

Resurrecting Voices: The Ethical, Social and Legal Implications of AI-Generated Music Using Deceased Artists

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1 Abstract

The purpose of this assignment is to highlight issues that involve emerging computing technologies. Therefore, this report analyses ethical, social, and legal issues relating to the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to generate the voices of deceased artists.

The structure is as follows: The first section is the Introduction which gives an overview on the problem statement and the upcoming points that follow.

Next we have the heart of the report, the Issues section discussing the issues centered around the report's topic in detail.

Lastly the report ends with a Conclusion which encapsulates all the points made in the report along with some personal recommendations on the issues discussed, followed by the References section, highlighting the various sources used for making of this report.

Figure 1: Articles showing instances of songs being made using vocals of late musicians: Hide (Left) (audioXpress (2014)) and Beatles John Lennon (Right) (Snapes (2023))

2 Introduction

Tupac Shakur, Amy Winehouse, Michael Jackson, and Elvis Presley what do these artists have in common? They all left an indelible mark on the music industry and, are all dead. However, in recent years, we have witnessed the rise of new compositions, covers or artificial shows that recreate their voices through artificial intelligence. Platforms such as TikTok and YouTube have become flooded with AI-generated songs where these late icons appear to perform contemporary hits, a technological feat that both fascinates and disturbs.

Figure 2: Elvis Evolution concert, depicting Elvis Presley using AI and holograms (Lukowski (2025))

Figure 3: Screenshot of thumbnail of a video, using Micheal Jackson's voice to sing a famous Indian song(Hindi AI Music (2024))

These digitally recreated vocals raise profound questions. Ethically, did these artists ever consent to their voice being used after death? Legally, what laws, if any, govern the ownership and use of an artist's voice or image once they are gone? And Socially, what impact might such synthetic recreations have on how the public perceives authenticity, artistry, and even mortality itself?

The following report explores these intricacies, examining the ethical, legal, and social implications of AI-generated music using deceased artists. It will analyse the aftermath of this phenomenon, its influence on public, and the evolving debate on whether such technology represents innovation or exploitation.

All in all, it is a case of digital resurrection that blurs the line between tribute and transgression.

3 Issues Arising from AI-Generated Voices

3.1

AI generation of human voices, got its breakthrough, usage-wise, through the rise of use of generative AI, in early 2020s.

Figure 4: AI market trends in Music Industry (Shalwa (2024))

However, the major event that sparked the conversation of the concern for usage of AI was the release of the song "Heart on my Sleeve" made by an anonymous Tiktok user named "Ghostwriter977, using the Weeknd and Drake's voices on the track (Robinson (2023)).

Figure 5: Ghostwriter977 Profile picture (Ghostwriter977 (2025))

The aftermath of the release lead to the discussion of advantages as well as issues regarding the usage of AI to make musical compositions, some of which are highlighted below:

3.2 Legal Issues

3.2.1 Copyright and Training Data

One of the most prominent issues is deciding the dataset to train these AI models since most of the time these models incorporate existing recordings, raising concerns about copyright infringement.

When AI is trained on copyrighted sound recordings, the output can be called a "derivative work" However, sometimes this output is often "new" in structure, making it hard to utilise infringement claims. Its also important to note that an AI replica of a voice may not directly use an original copyrighted work, further blurring liability. (Shroff (2024))

3.2.2 Personality Rights

In the United Kingdom (UK), there is no dedicated set of personality or publicity rights. Therefore, an individual's identity is not automatically protected by law. (HM Revenue & Customs (n.d.a))

Although certain aspects of a person's public persona can be protected through trade mark registration such as celebrity names, stage names, stylised signatures, logos, (or similar, incorporating their likeness) (Novagraaf (2024)), these mechanisms still do not extend to protecting a person's "natural voice". As a result, legal actions against AI-generated voice cloning in the UK (much like some other areas of the world) remain complex and limited.

Without a statutory publicity right, claimants are generally forced to rely on tort-based actions, most commonly passing off, which requires proving goodwill, misrepresentation, and damage, criteria that are very susceptible to external factors and are hard to satisfy in cases AI-generated music in general. (HM Revenue & Customs (n.d.b))

3.2.3 Authority and Ownership

Works of music made through AI have an interesting and almost awkward place when it comes to authorship. With the surge of this technology, the lack of concrete laws, and the ethical ambiguity around how training data is even gathered in the first place, it becomes unclear who actually has authority over an AI-generated work. Is it the person who produced the track using the AI? The AI company? The data owners such as the estate that owns the music the AI was trained on? The artist themselves, or any living kin in the case of deceased creators? All of this makes the legal boundaries even blurrier. (Battistella & Rossi (2023))

3.2.4 Recent Legal events

One of the biggest events that really captured the issues around AI-generated music :— its use, its problems, and the legal fallout, was when Drake released Taylor Made Freestyle, a diss-track aimed at Kendrick Lamar during their now-finished feud in early 2024. The track used AI-generated voices of Snoop Dogg and the late Tupac Shakur. As expected, things escalated quickly: the song was taken down after Tupac’s estate issued a cease-and-desist letter, arguing that the use of his likeness and voice was a misrepresentation.(Horowitz (2024))

Figure 6: Figure showing Drake (Left), Kendrick Lamar (Middle) and Tupac (Right) (Moore (2024))

3.2.5 New Legislative and Regulatory Trends

The legal landscape is beginning to respond. The UK’s All-Party Parliamentary Group (APPG) on Music has recommended introducing a specific personality right covering Voice, Image, Name, and Likeness (VINL) to protect against AI misuse (UK Music (2024)). Similarly, several copyright offices and legislatures worldwide are evaluating reforms to clarify artists’ control over AI-generated replicas.

In the United States of America (USA), for example, Tennessee’s Ensuring Likeness, Voice and Image Security (ELVIS) Act (Ensuring Likeness, Voice, and Image Security Act) directly targets generative AI voice replication by expanding the right of publicity to cover unauthorised digital voice facsimiles and imposing liability on services that create or distribute such replicas without consent.(Armstrong Advisory (2024))

3.3 Ethical Issues

3.3.1 Consent

One of the core ethical dilemmas arises from the fact that the artists are no longer alive and, therefore, could never have consented to the use of their voices, even for AI training on their existing music, let alone for generating entirely new compositions. This ethical tension is not limited to AI-generated music; it also extends to posthumous

decisions regarding their original works, where choices about distribution, remixing, or commercialisation are made without the artist's input or approval.

Figure 7: Example of a posthumous album (Balloonersims by Mac Miller(Miller (2025))

3.3.2 Respect & Legacy

Music generated posthumously can be used by the user to taint an artist's legacy, or maybe using an artist's reputation to spread a message that they may not have condoned or even been aware of.

One of the clearest examples of this is previously mentioned:-Drake's "Taylor Made Freestyle," where AI-generated vocals mimicking Tupac are used to deliver lines and commentary that the real Tupac, had he been alive today, may never have expressed.(Genius (2024))

[Verse 1: 2Pac (AI)]
Kendrick, we need ya, the West Coast savior
Engraving your name in some hip-hop history
If you deal with this viciously
You seem a little nervous about all the publicity

Figure 8: Screenshot of a section of AI Tupac's lyrics in "Taylor made Freestyle" (Genius (2024))

3.3.3 Monetary Advantages

There are situations where the owners of a late artist's estate may choose to release AI-generated music or covers primarily for financial gain, even when the public, or the

artist's own family opposes such uses. In these cases, the commercial incentives of the estate or associated companies may outweigh considerations of artistic integrity, consent, or the preservation of the artist's legacy.

3.3.4 Positive side

On the positive side, preserving an artists memory after their demise has been relied on their works' existence on the Internet in this day and age. Therefore use of AI to maybe remake an artists lost songs, key compositions can help a musician to be alive, virtually for years to come.

3.4 Social Issues

3.4.1 Fan and Public Perception

AI-generated songs can significantly shape how fans and the wider public remember an artist. When AI produces music or lyrics that do not reflect the artist's real creative style, values, or personality, it risks distorting their legacy

3.4.2 Family and Estate Impact

As covered in earlier sections, an artist's family and estate can become vulnerable to legal disputes, emotional distress, and even public scrutiny when AI-generated music is released without considering their wishes or the legacy they are trying to protect. In many cases, the burden of challenging unauthorised AI recreations falls directly on the family, placing them in difficult and highly publicised situations.

3.4.3 Lack of creativity

With the rise of AI-generated music, there is a growing concern that upcoming artists may become less creative in their own compositions. Instead of exploring real tracks made by past musicians, they could simply generate songs "in the style of" a particular artist and rely on that as a shortcut for inspiration. In the long run, this risks weakening the boundary between inspiration and exploitation, especially when the output imitates a late artist's voice, style, or musical identity too closely.

3.4.4 Access and Equity

Only wealthy estates are likely to benefit from AI-based "resurrections," since they have the financial resources, legal teams, and industry connections to commercialise an artist's legacy. This creates an uneven playing field where lesser known or independent artists are marginalised, as AI technologies may be used primarily for profit rather than for supporting or uplifting emerging talent.

4 Conclusion

4.1 Summary of Findings

Legally, there is a need for laws protecting an individual's personal features like their looks, voice and more, in this surge of AI generated content, like Deepfakes, photos etc. and not just vocal impersonations. Moreover, the confusion regarding ownership also persists. Instances of UK APPG's VINL recommendations and USA's ELVIS Act show a way to tackle these issues. Ethically, concerns center around consent of the artists, its impact on an artist's legacy and the dilemma, family of the artists, their fans and estates face while dealing with these issues. Socially, AI resurrection has the capability to make or break a late musician's image and legacy with respect to the coming age of people being exposed to their (the artist's) works.

Therefore, usage of AI should be dealt with care and respect so as to entertain these said issues.

4.2 Personal Recommendations

With the main issues discussed here are some personal takes to tackle the landscape of GenAI: a

4.2.1 Legal Reform

- Introduce or strengthen personality rights covering voice, image, and likeness.
- Require licensing or permission for AI voice cloning.

4.2.2 Ethical Guidelines

- Establish ethical codes covering AI Music Generation.
- Require watermarking or disclaimers for AI-generated voice content.
- Encourage artists (or estates/families of late artists) to set AI usage rules for their own works during their lifetime .

4.2.3 Social Protections

- Platforms should detect and label AI-generated voice media.
- Conduct public education campaigns on AI generated media such as Videos, images and Songs .
- Support educational use of AI in culturally respectful ways in educational institutions .

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